

GOLIZIN-KRYLOV METHOD FOR $A(z)$ -ANALYTIC FUNCTION

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Annotatsiya. Ma'lumki, soha chegarasidagi qiymatlarini bilgan holda uning soha ichkarisidagi qiymatlarini tiklash masalaridan bo'lib, bu mavzuni o'rganishga ko'plab ilmiy adabiyotlar va maqolalar bag'ishlangan. Tekislikda bu masalani funksiyaning qiymatlari sohaning butun chegarasida berilgan holda Koshining integral formulasi yechadi. Funksiyaning qiymatlari sohaning butun chegarasida emas, faqatgina chegaraning biror qismidagina berilgan bo'lsa masala qiyinlashadi. Agar bu masala $A(z)$ –analitik funksiya uchun ko'rilsa, qaralayotgan sinf yanada kengayib, imkoniyatimiz yanada oshadi.

Annotation. As you know, it is one of the issues of restoring the values within the field, knowing its values within the field, and a lot of scientific literature and articles have been devoted to the study of this topic. In the plane, this problem is solved by Cauchy's integral formula, where the values of the function are given at the whole boundary of the field. The problem is complicated if the values of the function are given only in a part of the boundary, and not in the whole boundary of the field. If this problem is considered for the $A(z)$ -analytic function, then the class under consideration expands and our chances increase.

Key words

- Limniskata.
- Carleman formula is appropriate.
- maximum principle

Suppose that the field, $\Omega \subset \mathbb{C}$ is given. Ω in the field

$$L(a; r) = \left\{ |\Psi(z; a)| = \left| z - a + \int_{\gamma(z; \xi)} \overline{A(\tau)} d\tau \right| < r \right\}$$

The set is called Limniskata. Wehere $a \in \Omega, r > 0 f \in H_A^p(L(a, r)), p = 1$, $L(a, r)$ Cauchy's integral formula is appropriate for limniscata.

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\partial L(a, r)} \frac{f(z)(d\xi + A(\xi)d\bar{\xi})}{\xi - z + \int_{\gamma(z, \xi)} \overline{A(\tau)} d\tau} \quad z \in L(a, r) \quad (1)$$

$\xi \in \partial L(a, r), z \in L(a, r)$ where we denote an arbitrary path from point ξ to point z by $\gamma(z, \xi)$. We now ask the problem of restoring the values of the analytical function $A(z)$ given by $M \subset \partial L(a, r)$ in the set of points in the domain. Using Carleman's idea, we construct an auxiliary function that frees the integration of formula (1) $L(a, r) \setminus M$. To do this, we introduce the auxiliary function $\varphi(z) = H_A^\infty L(a, r)$, which satisfies the following 2 conditions

1. $|\varphi(\xi)| = 1$ all $\partial L(a, r) \setminus M$
2. $|\varphi(z)| > 1$ all $L(a, r)$

Teorema.1. If $f \in H^p(L(a, r))$ and $M \in \partial L(a, r)$ has a positive dimension in the Lebeg sense, then for all $z \in \partial L(a, r)$ the following Carleman formula is appropriate.

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \int_M f(t) \left[\frac{\varphi(\xi)}{\varphi(z)} \right]^m \frac{(d\xi + A(\xi)d\bar{\xi})}{\xi - z + \int_{\gamma(z, \xi)} \overline{A(\tau)} d\tau} \quad (2)$$

Proof. $f\varphi^m$ function $A(z)$ -analytic, m -arbitrary integer in Hardy space. In this case, $H_A^p(L(a, r))$, the Cauchy integral is defined as follows.

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\partial L(a, r)} \frac{f(z)(d\xi + A(\xi)d\bar{\xi})}{\xi - z + \int_{\gamma(z, \xi)} \overline{A(\tau)} d\tau} \quad z \in L(a, r)$$

Divide this integral into two sets M va $\partial L(a, r) \setminus M$ and form the following expression.

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_M \frac{f(\xi)(d + A(\xi)d\bar{\xi})}{\xi - z + \int_{\gamma(z,\xi)} \overline{A(\tau)}d\tau} + \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\partial L(a,r)/M} \frac{f(\xi)(d\xi + A(\xi)d\bar{\xi})}{\xi - z + \int_{\gamma(z,\xi)} \overline{A(\tau)}d\tau}$$

Here $f(\xi) \left[\frac{\varphi(\xi)}{\varphi(z)} \right]^m$ is an integrable function.

According to the maximum principle of the module, the function $f(\xi)$ reaches a maximum at the limit of $\partial L(a, r)$. $\max_{\xi \in \partial L(a,r)} |f(\xi)| = B$ In this case, the following place (z) : $\left| \frac{\varphi(\xi)}{\varphi(z)} \right| \leq q < 1$ and the following we get the result.

$$\left| f(\xi) \left[\frac{\varphi(\xi)}{\varphi(z)} \right]^m \right| \leq Bq^m \rightarrow 0, \quad m \rightarrow \infty$$

$$\begin{aligned} f(z) &= \frac{1}{2\pi i} \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \int_M f(\xi) \left[\frac{\varphi(\xi)}{\varphi(z)} \right]^m \frac{(d\xi + A(\xi)d\bar{\xi})}{\xi - z + \int_{\gamma(z,\xi)} \overline{A(\tau)}d\tau} \\ &+ \frac{1}{2\pi i} \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\partial L(a,r)/M} f(\xi) \left[\frac{\varphi(\xi)}{\varphi(z)} \right]^m \frac{(d\xi + A(\xi)d\bar{\xi})}{\xi - z + \int_{\gamma(z,\xi)} \overline{A(\tau)}d\tau} \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi i} \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \int_M f(\xi) \left[\frac{\varphi(\xi)}{\varphi(z)} \right]^m \frac{(d\xi + A(\xi)d\bar{\xi})}{\xi - z + \int_{\gamma(z,\xi)} \overline{A(\tau)}d\tau} + 0 \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi i} \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \int_M f(\xi) \left[\frac{\varphi(\xi)}{\varphi(z)} \right]^m \frac{(d\xi + A(\xi)d\bar{\xi})}{\xi - z + \int_{\gamma(z,\xi)} \overline{A(\tau)}d\tau} \end{aligned}$$

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \int_M f(t) \left[\frac{\varphi(\xi)}{\varphi(z)} \right]^m \frac{(d\xi + A(\xi)d\bar{\xi})}{\xi - z + \int_{\gamma(z,\xi)} \overline{A(\tau)}d\tau} \text{ hence the formula}$$

proved.

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